

WORKPLACE HARMONY AND WORKERS PRODUCTIVITY CHALLENGES IN THE OIL AND GAS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study investigated the relationship between Workplace Harmony and Workers Productivity Challenges in the oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study adopted the Survey/Cross sectional method. The chosen dimensions Workplace Harmony adopted in the study are : Incidence of Strike, Low grievance and Incidence of Lock out. The Population of study is made up of all the listed oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NGX) for the period 2015-2021, consisting of 11 companies The major research instrument is the questionnaire. The study developed hypotheses and the hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) with the aid of statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21 soft ware. The findings of the tested hypotheses indicated that there are low positive relationship between the dimension of workplace harmony and workers productivity challenges in the oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Deriving from the findings the research conclude that there is a low positive relationship between workers productivity challenges and workplace harmony. Similarly, the researchers recommends that the managers or owners of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria should periodically negotiate with the labour union representatives in order to resolve contending issues thereby producing an atmosphere of workplace harmony and in order to avoid the incidence of strike, the managers of the oil and gas companies , should always engage the workers by having a fruitful communication with the workers in the company individually or through their labour union representative on issues that has to be address and that can lead to industrial dispute if not properly handled.

Keywords: Workplace Harmony, Incidence of Strike, Workers Challenges, Productivity measures.

1. INTRODUCTION

The incessant grievance and disputes between management and employee in the oil and gas companies has more than ever before been publicized in the manifestation of negative consequences such as decline in the performance of the organization and that of the employee. Arguably, it is observed that management of oil and gas companies in Nigeria practice management of exclusionism, neglect of power sharing mechanisms which ensure partnership amongst stakeholders in the workplace. This derogation of organizational communication pattern breed disharmony in the industry.

Workplace harmony refers to a friendly and cooperative agreement on working relationships between employers and employees for their mutual benefit (Otobo, 2005; Osad & Osas, 2013). According to Puttapalli and Vuram (2012), Workplace harmony is concerned with the relationship between management and employees with respect to the terms and conditions of employment and the work place. In effect, it is a situation where employees and management cooperate willingly in pursuit of the organization's aims and objectives.

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A pure state of workplace harmony scarcely exists in the oil and gas sub-sector, as grievance between employees and management erodes the set objectives of the organizations. It seems that the managers of these organizations believe too much in their ability and ego. It also seems they believe in dishing out orders, directives and policies to the workers. They failed to involve employees in all policy process. In some cases they make decisions not minding its implication on the people who are to implement them. Social relations in these firms are creamed in master servant power chain to such an extent that the employee has no close ties with the owners of work, or its agents. Orders are given using the steam shovel approach such that no one worker is allowed to know the reason for any decision that affects the tasks they do.

Employee working under such organizational climate feel dissatisfied as the managements of these organizations are only concerned about the organization and not considering how the employees feels. Such organizational culture breeds disharmony between management and employee. These seem to lead to low employee engagement, loyalty and employee satisfaction in the organization. Iheriohanma (2007) asserts that management practice of exclusionism, neglect of power sharing mechanism which ensures partnership amongst stakeholders in the workplace and derogation of organizational communication pattern may breed disharmony in contemporary organizations

The conditions of employment, have been inadequate with respect to the area of job security, redundancy, health, welfare and safety of workers are not favourable to the employee. most of the employees in the industry complained that their hard work and commitment are not always put into consideration when the organization wants to downsize rather the management attach some elements of organizational politics. In the area of health, welfare and safety of workers the policy are made in favour of the organization and management are not always committed to it.

These have led to employees exhibiting such attitudes as lack of cooperation and withdrawal attitude of the employees in the place of work, reduced commitment and increased intent to leave by employees. Other visible symptoms are bad tempered behaviour and appearance, moodiness, worry and tension, insubordination, increase in wastage and decline in productivity of the worker who indulges in self criticism, develops negativism and in extreme cases tries to destroy the valuable property of the organization. At the worse conflict/dispute arises between management and the employees.

Workers productivity performance suffer as employees whose intention is to leave at every given opportunity may not put in their best in the organization as the loyalty of such an employee may not lie with the organization. This could be responsible for delayed production, increase in equipment breakdown and excess expenditure in replacing and training new employees.

Despite the immense contribution of the oil and gas firms to the growth of Nigerian Economy and the south-south region in particular, through the creation of employment, income generation for government, tax, GDP and food security, the potentials inherent in this industry appear thwarted by the nature of workplace harmony in these organizations. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to ascertain the extent to which workplace harmony relates with workers productivity in the listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Purpose and Objectives of the Study.

The main purpose of the Study is to examine the relationship between workplace Harmony and employees productivity challenges .The other objectives are as follows;

1. to examine the relationship between workplace Harmony and work environment challenges
2. to examine the relationship between workplace Harmony and Human Capital development Challenges
3. to examine the relationship between workplace Harmony and Technological advancement challenges .

Research Questions. The following research questions are meant to guide the study. the research questions are in consonant with the stated objectives of the study.

1. to what extent does workplace harmony relates with Work Environment challenges?
2. to what extent does workplace harmony relates with Human Capital Development challenges?
3. to what extent does workplace harmony relate with Technological Advancement challenges ?

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Frustration-Aggression theory

The theoretical framework of this research work was anchored on Frustration-Aggression theory of conflict. This theory was developed by John Dollard and his associates in 1939, and has been reformed or amended by other scholars such as Leonard Berkowitz (1962) and Aubrey Yates (1962). This theory appears to be the most common explanation for violent behaviour stemming from inability to fulfill needs. The theory used the psychological theories of motivation and behaviour as well as frustration and aggression. In an attempt to explain aggression to mean the difference between what people feel they want or deserve to what they actually get-the-want-get- ratio, and difference between expected need satisfaction and actual need satisfaction (David, 2006). This implies that where expectation does not meet attainment, the tendency is for people to confront those they hold responsible for frustrating their ambitions. The main explanation that the frustration-aggression theory provides that aggression is not just undertaken as a natural reaction or instinct, but it is outcomes of frustration and that in a situation where the legitimate desires of an individual is denied either directly or by the indirect consequence of the way organization or society is structured, the feeling of disappointment may lead such a person to express his anger through violence that will be directed at those he/she holds responsible or people who are directly or indirectly related to them.

The assumptions of this theory were that aggression arises as a result of depriving or blocking of people efforts in attaining their personal goals leading to frustration; that the occurrence of aggressive behaviour always precedes or presupposes the existence of frustration and existence of frustration always leads to form of aggression; it also assume that frustration causes aggression, but when the source (s) of the frustration cannot be challenged, the aggression gets displaced onto an innocent target; the theory also assume that while frustration prompts a behaviour or change in attitude that may or may not be aggressive, any aggressive behaviour is the direct result of frustration, making frustration not adequate or sufficient, but a necessary condition for aggression. This is to say that frustration creates a need to respond to, and some form of aggression is one possible outcome of frustration

In situations where feelings of frustration become widespread among the parties and the feeling is that people are getting less than they deserve, the most common advice is that government or political leaders can do is to find out what the expectations of such individuals and groups are and to seek ways of negotiating with them. However, in most situations, those in a position of authority believe that giving in to public demands or entering into negotiations is a sign of weakness, just in the cases of ASUU and federal government as well as NLC and federal government in Nigeria. However, a typical example of the manner in which frustration leads to aggression that in turn creates disputes can be seen in the ongoing crises in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria. After waiting patiently and peacefully agitating for what the people of the region considered as a fair share of the oil wealth that is exploited from their land, youths now take the law into their own hands by vandalizing oil pipelines, kidnapping oil workers for large amount of money and generating problems for those they believe are responsible for their predicaments. The value of this theory in the study is that a particular frustration instigates aggression fundamentally against the expectations of the parties involved or the sources of frustration constituting the primary outcomes of aggression.

Concept of Workplace Harmony

According to Puttapalli and Vuram (2012), workplace harmony is concerned with the relationship between management and employees with respect to the terms and conditions of employment and the work place. In effect, it is a situation where employees and management cooperate willingly in pursuit of the organization's aims and objectives. Workplace harmony requires that: i. All management personnel understand their responsibilities and what is required of them, and have the training and authority necessary to discharge such duties and responsibilities efficiently; ii. Duties and responsibilities for each group of employees are stated with clarity and simplicity in the organizational/institutional structure; iii. Individual employees or work-groups know their objectives and are regularly kept informed of progress made towards achieving them; iv. There is an effective link in the interchange of information and views between senior management and members of the work group; v. Supervisors are briefed about innovation and changes before they occur so they can explain management's policies and intentions to the work-group; vi. Employers cooperate with trade unions in establishing effective procedures for the negotiation of terms and conditions of employment and for the settlement of disputes; vii. Employers encourage the establishment of effective procedures among member organizations/institutions for the settlement of grievances and

disputes at the level of the establishment or undertaking; viii. Employers take all reasonable steps to ensure the organization/institution observes agreements and agreed upon procedures; ix. The organization/institution maintains a communication system, which secures the interchange of information and views between different levels in the organization/institution and ensures that employees are systematically and regularly kept informed, factually and objectively, of changes and progress in the system.

Workplace harmony thus covers the area of responsibilities, employment policy, collective bargaining, communication and consultation (Odia & Omofonmwan, 2007). Workplace harmony enhances labour productivity and in turn improves performance in all sector, achieving economic growth, and enhancing living standards and quality of life. It creates a peaceful working environment conducive to tolerance, dialogue and other alternative (to strike) means of resolving workplace or labour disputes in Nigeria (such as negotiation, mediation, arbitration, conciliation and litigation or court adjudication). This creates a high level of employee satisfaction.

Sayles and Strauss (1981) assert that with the inevitable differences among groups within an organization, conflict and differing objectives permeate modern organizations. This type of conflict prevents the existence of workplace harmony which reflects a state of organizational instability (Sayles & Strauss, 2009). On the other hand, Hanson (2006) opines that workplace harmony represents absence of strike by workplace unions in organization which is bound to result in effective and efficient organization.

Workplace harmony thus covers four broad areas of cooperation: responsibilities, employment policy, collective bargaining, communication and consultation (Odia & Omofonmwan, 2007). Workplace Harmony can only come out of what is known as "Workplace Democracy" a situation in organisation where to a larger extent, the participation of workers is adequately sought in the process of making decisions that will determine the conditions of their working lives. It involves joint participation in decision making process between the two major actors to labour relations. It encompasses such concepts as joint consultation, co-ownership or co-partnership, co-determination and whitleyism (Otobo 2005). Workplace harmony enhances labour productivity and in turn improves performance in organizations, achieving economic growth, and enhancing living standards and quality of life. It creates a peaceful working environment conducive to tolerance, dialogue and other alternative (to strike) means of resolving workplace or labour disputes in Nigeria (such as negotiation, mediation, arbitration, conciliation and litigation or court adjudication). This creates a high level of employee satisfaction.

Workplace/organizational harmony refers to a friendly and cooperative agreement on working relationships between employers and employees for their mutual benefit (Laden, 2012). According to Puttapalli and Vuram (2012), workplace/organizational harmony is concerned with the relationship between management and employees with respect to the terms and conditions of the employment and the work place. In effect, it is a situation where employees and management cooperate willingly in pursuit of the organization's aims and objectives. The dimensions of the social harmony in the organization completes with the mutual trust, faith, believe, understanding, ethical behavior, cooperation, coordination, collaboration, commonness, helpfulness, peacefulness etc.

Workplace/organizational harmony requires that: i. All management personnel understand their responsibilities and what is required of them, and have the training and authority necessary to discharge such duties and responsibilities efficiently; ii. Duties and responsibilities for each group of employees are stated with clarity and simplicity in the organizational structure; iii. Individual employees or work-groups know their objectives and are regularly kept informed of progress made towards achieving them; iv. There is an effective link in the interchange of information and views between senior management and members of the work group; v Employers cooperate with trade unions in establishing effective procedures for the negotiation of terms and conditions of employment and for the settlement of disputes; vi. Employers encourage the establishment of effective procedures among member organizations for the settlement of grievances and disputes at the level of the establishment or undertaking, and , vii. The organization maintains a communication system which secures the interchange of information and views between different levels in the organization and ensures that employees are systematically and regularly kept informed, factually and objectively, of changes and progress in the system.

Workplace/organizational harmony therefore covers four broad areas of cooperation: responsibilities, employment policy, collective bargaining, communication and consultation. Workplace/organizational harmony enhances labor productivity and in turn improves performance , achieving economic growth, and enhancing living standards and quality of life.

The term workplace harmony is made up of two words – workplace and harmony. Workplace means the process of productivity-activity in which an individual is (or a group of individuals are) engaged, while harmony is the peaceful co-existence between two parties (of opposing interests) in an organization. According to Otobo (2000), workplace harmony refers to a friendly and co-operative agreement on working relationship between the employer and the employees intended for their mutual benefits in an organization. Awuzie (2010) believes that workplace harmony is an ideal state of peace existing between the employer and employees that will prompt them to engage in the production of goods and services in an organization. This is because employees are motivated by the existing harmonious relationship to give the best of their talents or potentials for the development and progress of the organization. The following are the indicative measures of workplace harmony. i. incidence of strike, ii. low grievance and iii. workers collaboration

The unpleasant side of workplace relation and on which the public often associate workplace union is strike. The strike shows a breakdown of cordial relationship between the employee represented by the labour union and employer or management. Strike are the most overt and significant aspect of workplace conflict. But they are unfortunately only a part of the phenomenon of conflict. Most strikes involved attempts by either the union or management to change the bargaining power of the other party. When a strike is adequately used for the demand of the employees, it can force employers to concede to the demands of the employees. It can impose exorbitant costs and thereby induce them to reach agreement. A strike may be used to effect a change in the structure of bargaining and to win substantive demand by workers. Isiaka (2001) examined the workplace relations practice in Nigeria and the continued relevance of strikes as a form of workplace action in Nigeria. He posited that the environment influences the actors, their goals, ideology, and power in an workplace relations system. This, in turn, influences the behavior of the actors, especially in the process of rule-making. He argued that a strike is a very important means of ensuring favorable employment conditions in Nigeria, and posited that the argument against the right to strike in the public sectors in Nigeria rests more on the impact of the strike on the economy, public health, and safety than on the sovereignty doctrine (Isiaka, 2001). Sovereignty is the supreme, absolute, and uncontrollable power by which any independent state is governed (Black, 2010).

Nwadike (2019) had a study on conflict management strategy and performance in the Nigerian Breweries Plc in South-East, Nigeria with particular reference to the Nigerian Breweries Plc in Onitsha, Owerri, Enugu and Aba. The objectives of the study were basically to investigate the effect of accommodating strategy, avoiding strategy, collaborating strategy and compromising strategy on organizational performance. The study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study was 1752 respondents of the Nigerian Breweries, Plc in the South-East zone of Nigeria. A sample of 337 respondents was drawn from the population using Borg and Gall (1973) formula, while the questionnaire response rate was 300 (80.65%). The hypotheses were tested by the use of Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient and Multiple Regression analysis through SPSS computer software version 21. The study revealed that accommodating strategy had a significant positive effect on organizational performance of Brewery companies in Nigeria, and that avoiding strategy had a significant negative effect on organizational performance. The study also revealed that collaborating strategy had a significant positive effect on organizational performance, and that compromising strategy had a significant positive effect on organizational performance. The study recommended that management of organizations should adopt collective bargaining in managing conflicts in order to be effective in solving organizational problems, and that organizations should try to adopt an inclusive collaborating strategy in conflict management and at the same time strive to involve union leadership/employee representatives in vital decisions that affect the workforce

Ekwoaba (2016) had a study on conflict management in government hospitals in Mainland Local Government Area of Lagos State. A sample size of 100 respondents was randomly selected. The data obtained was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, simple percentage with the used of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 15. The study revealed that causes of conflict includes poor working conditions; poor government remuneration; non-fulfillment of promises by management and government; delay in payment of bonuses and allowances; inadequate medical facilities and infrastructures; disagreement between management and workers' representative on management style and refusal of government to implement collective agreement. It is suggested that the negative effects of conflict can be addressed by adopting appropriate mechanisms, styles and strategies of collective agreement implementation; collaboration between management and workers representatives; prompt payment of salaries as well as joint decision making between management and employees

Osabiya (2015) conducted a study on conflict management and resolution in Nigeria public sector. The study adopted experimental survey design. Percentages and frequencies were used to analyze the responses collected from the respondents. The study adopted descriptive statistics. The population of the study was 170 employees. The study revealed that conflict

can be resolved through compromise between the employees and management. That leadership styles adopted can also lead to conflict in the organization. The study recommended that workers should be involved in decision-making process in Nigeria public service so as to reduce the rate of disputes or conflict. It was concluded that there should be effective communication network between the workers and the management.

Wilson (2019) examined empirical analysis of the causes and effects of workplace conflicts in public hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria, 2009-2014, using University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) and Braithwaite Memorial Hospital (BMH). The population was 240. The sample size was 224 respondents from the two hospitals. The data was presented using table with percentages of frequency. The study found that poor communication between individuals and groups, personality clashes, poor management policies, scarcity of resources, and non-implementation of service circulars, are the major causes of the conflicts in the public hospitals. The study also revealed that conflicts have a significant impact on the operations of the UPTH and BMH. The study recommended that strategies should be adopted to reduce workplace conflict and enhance productivity in Rivers State public hospitals. Said, Mori, Bidrul, Ali, Yusof and Mat (2016) had a study on the relationship between workplace conflict and job performance using staff in Terengganu higher learning institution as a case study. The study adopted convenience sampling technique. The study adopted Pearson Correlation Coefficient and multiple regression analysis to test hypotheses. The study revealed that conflict in communication, organizational structure and personality affect job performance in an organization. The study also revealed that communication is the major factor that affect conflict and job performance. The study also showed that there was a moderate positive relationship existing between communication and job performance. The study recommended that the organization should increase their level of communication in order to reduce the conflict among employees so that employees can perform well in their jobs. Mayowa (2015) carried out a study on industrial conflict and its management strategies in selected manufacturing companies. The study revealed that the causes of conflict in manufacturing companies in Lagos State, Nigeria include poor means of communicating grievances to top managers, unfavorable economic and industrial policies, poor employee compensation and welfare among others. The study concluded that managers should combine strategies such as bargaining, collaboration and avoidance when dealing with industrial conflict to maintain cordial and productive labour-management relationship.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research work is basically a survey; the survey type is cross sectional. A cross sectional survey examines the relationship between the variables of interest as they exist in a defined population at a single point in time. The cross sectional survey is considered the best fit for this study. therefore, primary data was used for the purpose of this study and for all the statistical analyses. The chosen dimensions Workplace Harmony adopted in the study are : Incidence of Strike, Low grievance and Incidence of Lock out. The Population of study is made up of all the listed oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NGX) for the period 2015-2021, consisting of 11 companies. The major research instrument is the questionnaire. The study developed hypotheses and the hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) with the aid of statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21 soft ware.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Hypothesis 1.

H₀₁: there is no significant relationship between incidence of strike and work productivity challenges in the oil and gas firms

Table 1: Relationship between productivity challenges and incidence of strike

	Prod. Chall..	Incidence of strike
Pearson Correlation	1	.245*
Sig. (2-tailed)		.046
N	67	67
Pearson Correlation	.245*	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.046	
N	67	67

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2022

The table above presents a Pearson Correlation coefficient r of .245*. A Pearson product moment correlation was conducted to evaluate the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Productivity and incidence of strike. Preliminary analysis showed assumption of normality and linearity. There is a significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a positive relationship between Productivity and incidence of strike of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria ($r=0.245^*, p<0.01$). This finding has provided solution to the research question number one.

Hypotheses 2

H02: there is no significant relationship between Workers productivity and low grievance in the oil and gas firms in Nigeria

Table 2: Relationship between Workers Productivity and low grievance

	Workers Prod.	Low grievance
Pearson Correlation	1	.337**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
N	67	67
Pearson Correlation	.337**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
N	67	67

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2022

The table above presents a Pearson Correlation coefficient r of .337**. A Pearson product moment correlation was conducted to evaluate the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between productivity and low grievance. Preliminary analysis showed assumption of normality and linearity. There is a significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a positive relationship between productivity and low grievance of workers of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria ($r=0.337^*, p<0.01$). This finding has provided solution to the research question number two.

Hypotheses 3

H03: there is no significant relationship between workers productivity and incidence of lockout in the oil and gas companies in Nigeria

Table 3: Relationship between Productivity and lock out

	Workers prod.	Lock out
Pearson Correlation	1	.079
Sig. (2-tailed)		.524
N	67	67
Pearson Correlation	.079	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.524	
N	67	67

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2022

The table above presents a Pearson Correlation coefficient r of .079. A Pearson product moment correlation was conducted to evaluate the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between productivity and lock out. Preliminary analysis showed assumption of normality and linearity. There is a significant evidence to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a very low positive relationship between productivity and incidence of lock out of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria. This finding has provided solution to the research question number three.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A Pearson product moment correlation was conducted to evaluate the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Productivity and incidence of strike. Preliminary analysis showed assumption of normality and linearity. There is a significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a positive relationship between Productivity and incidence of strike in the oil and gas companies in Nigeria ($r=0.245^*, p<0.01$). This finding has provided solution to the research question number one. Interestingly, the workplace of today is characterized by two opposing trends. On the one hand, employees are given leeway in the way they dress and act. The challenge of modern day business is increasing awareness on the part of employees about their rights and privileges. The rise in this awareness has become a pain in the

neck of growing management to such concerns that it attempts to diminish the glory of capitalistic mindedness that once bestride the pathway to managing like a colossus. A good and harmonious working environment is one where all workers are treated with dignity and respect, and where no worker is subjected to harassment by conduct that is related to religious belief or political opinion. Again the same principles will apply with regard to the promotion of a good and harmonious working environment on grounds of race, gender, disability, sexual orientation and age. For the purpose of this study, workplace harmony has been used interchangeably with industrial harmony. Commonsense dictates that what will define a good and harmonious working environment may change over time and place.

There is a significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a positive relationship between productivity and low grievance of workers of the oil and gas companies in south-south, Nigeria($r=0.337^*$, $p<0.01$). This finding has provided solution to the research question number two. Workplace harmony seems to be affected by this development that the frequency of management-workforce conflicts is fast raising in many sectors of world economies. The Nigeria workplace context had for decades been embattled in the demands for increased wage and earnings as means of incentivization as well as bonuses, awards, health packages etc which form the components of financial motivation. (Akinwade (2011).Inspite of these provisions, there is still manifest disaffection between employees on one strand and between management and employees on the other.

Industrial amicability alludes to a situation of peace in relative sense in any industrial organization, which includes; nonappearance of strikes, and doubt among work gatherings or unions, tranquil relationship amongst unions and administration of the organization, and additionally representative positive view of his or her commitment as member not as subject inside the organization. Work place harmony is an exceptionally basic element of organizational profitability and execution.

Industrial agreement in its optimal structure, presupposes an industry in a state of relative balance where relationship amongst people as well as gatherings are heartfelt and profitable. Sayles and Strauss (1981) noticed that with the unavoidable contrasts among gatherings inside an organization, struggle and varying destinations saturate cutting edge organizations. This kind of contention keeps the presence of work agreement which mirrors a condition of authoritative shakiness (Sayles and Strauss, 1981). Furthermore, as Hanson (1972) noted, industrial agreement speaks to nonappearance of conflict by industrial unions which will undoubtedly bring about viable and proficient organization.

There is a significant evidence to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a very low positive relationship between productivity and incidence of lock out of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria. This finding has provided solution to the research question number three. Furthermore, Puttapalli and Vuram (2012) defined workplace harmony as being concerned with the mutual relationship between management team and employees in relation to the terms and conditions of employment at the workplace. It is a situation where there is healthy and cooperative working relationship between employers and employees. And as such, implies that whenever these mutual expectations are breached by either parties, industrial relations tend to be strained, ending up in industrial disharmony or conflict (Bankole, 2000); and consequently, manifests in the form of open hostility, distrust, disrespect, noncooperation and avoidance of interaction (Hatch & Cunliffe, 2013). However, in order to mitigate or probably avert this scenario, Akpoyovwaire (2013) contends that people at the helm of affairs (management staff) must have the prerequisite knowledge and authority to execute their responsibilities objectively without fair or favor; they must ensure that the task structure of each employee group is properly defined in such a way that it leaves no room for role ambiguity; that employers of labor should synergize with trade union representatives in the development of effective procedures for negotiation of terms and conditions of employment and for settlement of disputes.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the study concludes that there exist a low positive relationship between Workplace Harmony and works productivity in the Oil and Gas firms in S Nigeria. Furthermore, base on the findings and conclusion of the study , the researchers recommends as follows:

1. That the managers of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria should periodically negotiate with the labour union representatives in order to resolve contending issues thereby producing an atmosphere of workplace harmony
2. In order to avoid the incidence of strike, the managers of the oil and gas companies, should continuously, engage by having a fruitful communication with the workers in the company individually or through their labour union representative on issues that has to be address and that can lead to industrial dispute if not properly handled.

3. Grievances of the workers in the oil and gas companies in south-south, Nigeria should always be attended to through continuous discussion between the managers of the organisation and the aggrieved workers.
4. The Company should always consider the adoption of a mediator when there are contending issues in the organization that has started creating the disruption of the organization industrial peaceful working environments and several issues of dispute negotiation as failed to address the contending issues on ground

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